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**A Comparative Study of Adjustment Level
of Regular and Contract Teachers Working
in Government Schools**

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A Comparative Study of Adjustment Level of Regular and Contract Teachers Working in Government Schools

Ritu Bala²⁶

Abstract

The fate of the pupils as well as the success or failure of an educational programme hangs on the degree of adjustment of the teacher. This research has focused on comparison of adjustment level of regular and contract Mathematics school teachers. Mangal Teacher Adjustment Inventory (M.T.A.I.) comprising of 70 items, designed for the preliminary assessment of the adjustment or maladjustment of the teachers belonging to Indian schools was used to find the level of adjustment of teachers. It was found that there is significant difference between the adjustment level of regular and contract teachers. It was also found that there is no significant difference between the teachers in relation to their gender and location as teachers working in government schools have the same social status and working environment. Effect of gender, location and interaction between type of recruitment and gender; type of recruitment and location; location and gender; type of recruitment, location and gender was found to insignificant.

Keywords

Adjustment Level, Teachers, Regular, Contract, Type of Recruitment

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Introduction

Use of contract teachers increased rapidly in India since the mid-1990s and there were 543,671 contract teachers in India in 2008-09. In Haryana, recruitment of teachers in the service is made 67% by direct recruitment on contract basis. The officially stated rationale for provision of contract teachers is to achieve three major equity and efficiency aims in an affordable way: expanding access to schooling in un-served communities; eliminating single-teacher schools and relieving multi-grade teaching; and reducing high pupil teacher ratios. Contract teacher schemes are favoured because they expand schooling access, increase teacher numbers, relieve multi-grade teaching and reduce class sizes in a fiscally manageable way. Although the schemes vary across states, generally contract teachers have renewable (often annually renewable) contracts rather than regular teachers' lifetime employment guarantees. Regular teacher pay scales are high. Nationally, contract teachers' salary rate in 2005 was on average about 35% of regular teachers' pay rate and have further fallen below 25% following Sixth Pay Commission related increases in regular teacher salaries (Kingdon and Sipahimalani-Rao, 2010).

Teachers are the most important input into schools; the relative effectiveness of contract and regular teachers raises educational quality and educational equity concerns. The quality aspect of education depends entirely on the character and personality of the teacher. A good teacher can communicate the divine spark of learning in a boon where as shallow one will achieve little even with the latest scientific aids. It is a fact that one good teacher can achieve more than a hundred bad or indifferent ones. The efficiency of a teacher is judged through her/his work and behaviour, which is very much dependent on the adjustment with her/him-self and her/his environment. A well-adjusted teacher is a source of inspiration to her/his students and a boon to the society. On the other hand, a maladjusted teacher can create havoc with her/his students and her/his own mental health.

In this way, the fate of the pupils as well as the success or failure of an educational programme hangs on the degree of adjustment of the teacher her/him-self. Higher level of adjustment of the teacher is directly linked with her/his efficiency in her/his work and a vital necessity for the welfare of the students and the nation in general.

Goyal (1980) in his doctoral research on “Relationship among Attitude, Job Satisfaction, Adjustment and Professional Interests of Teacher Educators in India” found that men and women differ significantly at .05 level in their social adjustment. Chattopadhyay and **Bhattacharya** (2002) found that subjects who were satisfied with their job reported higher job effectiveness and better social and emotional adjustment compared to those who were dissatisfied. Priyadarshani, Nibedita (2004) in her study found that the primary school teachers in the tribal area have been found to have average level of job satisfaction, moderate to high level of occupational stress and are highly committed to their profession. She also found significant three-factor interaction of sex, marital status, and professional commitment on teacher’s job satisfaction. Yadav, R. C. (2011) conducted a study on adjustment of secondary school teachers and observed no significant difference between male and female, rural and urban secondary school teachers. Goyat (2012) carried out a study to know the gender, demographical and educational impact on teachers adjustment behaviour and observed that there is no significant difference between male, female and rural, urban primary school teachers. Ritu Bala (2012) in her study found that there is no significant difference in the adjustment level of high school teachers in relation to their gender and location.

Therefore, if we wish to achieve the rationale for provision of contract teachers aimed to achieve quality in school education, we have to compare the adjustment level of regular and contract teacher and identify poorly adjusted teachers and take effective

remedial measures to enrich the school education. Present study focused on comparison of regular and contract schoolteachers working in Govt. schools.

Objectives of the Study

1. To compare the adjustment levels of regular and contract teachers working in government schools of Haryana.
2. To compare the adjustment levels of male and female teachers working in government schools of Haryana.
3. To compare the adjustment levels of urban and rural teachers working in government schools of Haryana.
4. To study the influence of type of service, location and gender on adjustment levels of teachers working in government schools of Haryana.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the adjustment levels of teachers in relation to their type of recruitment.
2. There is no significant difference between the adjustment levels of teachers in relation to their gender.
3. There is no significant difference between adjustment levels of teachers in relation to their location.
4. There is no significant interaction between type of recruitment and gender.
5. There is no significant interaction between type of recruitment and location.
6. There is no significant interaction between location and gender.
7. There is no significant interaction between type of recruitment, gender and location.

Delimitations

1. The study is confined to the state of Haryana.
2. The study is confined to the teachers working at elementary school stage.

Methodology

Considering the nature of the problem under investigation descriptive survey method of research was used.

Sampling

The population of the study was elementary school teachers working in Government Schools of Haryana. A sample consisting of 200 teachers was drawn using random sampling technique.

Table 1

Distribution of Sample

	Urban		Rural	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Regular	25	25	25	25
Contract	25	25	25	25

Tool

Mangal Teacher Adjustment Inventory (M.T.A.I.) comprising of 70 items, designed for the preliminary assessment of the adjustment or maladjustment of the

teachers of both sexes belonging to Indian schools made by S.K. Mangal was used to find the level of adjustment of teachers.

Data Collection

The researcher personally visited the schools and collected data from the teachers. The teachers were given M.T.A.T. and they were asked to fill up the same.

Analysis and Statistical Treatment of Data

Three way ANOVA was used to interpret the data. The summary of ANOVA for the present study is given the following tables 2:

Table 2

Summary of ANOVA

Sources of Variation	df	SS	MS	F	SIG
Type of Recruitment	1	300.13	300.13	17.18	.01
Gender	1	0.24	0.24	0.01	n.s.
Location	1	3.65	3.65	0.21	n.s.
Type of Recruitment *Gender	1	22.44	22.44	1.28	n.s.
Type of Recruitment* Location	1	1.44	1.44	0.08	n.s.
Location*Gender	1	13.00	13.00	0.74	n.s.

Type of Recruitment * Gender* Location	1	12.01	12.01	0.69	n.s.
With in	192	3353.68	17.47		
Total	199				

Table value: $.05F_{(1,192)} = 3.89$ and $.01F_{(1,192)} = 6.76$

Findings

1. Effect of gender, location and interaction between type of recruitment and gender; type of recruitment and location; location and gender; type of recruitment, location and gender was found to insignificant. Therefore, the null hypotheses: there is no significant difference between the adjustment levels of teachers in relation to their gender; there is no significant difference between adjustment levels of teachers in relation to their location; there is no significant interaction between type of recruitment and gender; there is no significant interaction between type of recruitment and location; there is no significant interaction between location and gender; there is no significant interaction between type of recruitment, gender and location are accepted.
2. Effect of type of recruitment on the adjustment level of teachers was found to be significant at .01 level. Therefore the hypothesis: there is no significant difference between the adjustment levels of teachers in relation to their type of recruitment is rejected.

Conclusions

Based on findings following conclusions were drawn:

1. There is significant difference between the adjustment levels of teachers in relation to their type of recruitment.
2. There is no significant difference between the adjustment levels of teachers in relation to their gender.
3. There is no significant difference between adjustment levels of teachers in relation to their location.
4. There is no significant interaction between type of recruitment and gender.
5. There is no significant interaction between type of recruitment and location.
6. There is no significant interaction between location and gender.
7. There is no significant interaction between type of recruitment, gender and location.

Suggestions

In the light of the findings of the present study, following are some suggestions that can be used by Government to improve the adjustment level of the teachers:

1. Contract school teachers should be paid salary on average about 75% of regular teachers' salary rate.
2. Contract teachers who perform their duties efficiently and sincerely should be given some incentives and awards.
3. Job of contract teachers who perform their duties efficiently and brings excellent results continuously for 7 years should be regularized.
4. Schoolteachers should not be overburdened by assigning those duties in surveys like surveys of population, surveys for elections, election duties etc.
5. Regular time based promotions should be adopted for regular as well as contract teachers.

6. The education of the children of contract schoolteachers should be made free in government institutions.
7. Professional and academic development programmes should be initiated for regular as well as contract teachers.

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